

D1.1 ArcSolution Kick-off meeting

Report

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ArcSolution

Arctic pollution in a One Health perspective
from complex challenges to sustainable solutions

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Cover: Group photo of all participants from Day One by Marta Anna Løvberg. Please note that not everyone attended both days, and some participants were not present for this photo.

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1 Summary of the deliverable

This deliverable covers the key outcomes of the ArcSolution kick-off meeting, held in Bodø, Norway, on October 23-24, 2024. It documents the event's organization, participants, agenda, and discussions.

2 Date and Venue and participants

The ArcSolution kick-off meeting took place at Nord University in Bodø, Norway, from October 23rd to 24th, 2024, with approximately 40 participants joining across the two days.

It was organized as a hybrid meeting with the possibility of online participation. Approximately 40 participants joined across the two days, including project participants, representatives of the city of Bodø, Nord University, international organizations and the Horizon Europe projects ILLUQ and ICEBERG. All project partners except Illisimatusarfik (University of Greenland) were represented in person, as well as the associated partners Memorial University (Canada) and Agroscope (Switzerland).

3 Day 1 – Vision, Policy and International Collaboration

The program began with a welcome address by Bodø's Mayor, Odd Emil Ingebrigtsen, who highlighted recent developments in Bodø, including its status as the European Capital of Culture for 2024, ongoing urban growth initiatives, a major new airport project, and green growth projects such as the city's electric container freight route.

Photo 1: Odd Emil Ingebrigtsen, the Mayor of Bodø, opened the kick-off meeting with an overview of the city, highlighting its key attributes and recent developments.

Nord University's role

The Dean of the Faculty for Biosciences and Aquaculture, Mette Sørensen (Nord University, Norway) welcomed ArcSolution to the University, and set the frame for the relevance of this important project in the overall strategy for the university and other research activities in the faculty. In many ways, One Health is the overall core research area for the faculty.

ArcSolution Vision and Goals

The scientific coordinator of ArcSolution, Jon Øyvind Odland (Nord University, Norway), presented the project's vision: to create a safer environment and enhance the quality of life for future generations through a One Health approach. Jon Øyvind Odland's presentation was based on his long-term work in the field of Arctic pollution and his personal experiences with the many challenges of ensuring a clean environment and healthy living conditions for the people in the Arctic. ArcSolution's vision is anchored in the Zero Pollution ambition, with the expectation that the project's findings will influence regulatory strategies and shape political agendas in the Arctic.

EU Policy Context

John Hanus, EU Policy Officer, outlined ArcSolution's place within the EU's strategic framework. He connected the project to major EU initiatives, including the European Green Deal, the Circular Economy Action Plan, and the Zero Pollution ambition. John Hanus also emphasized ArcSolution's alignment with the EU's broad research and innovation portfolio, which includes significant funding for polar, Arctic, and Antarctic studies aimed at addressing urgent global challenges.

John Hanus encouraged ArcSolution to join the EU Polar Cluster and highlighted the importance of engaging with EU policy objectives, particularly in the areas of Arctic Policy and Zero Pollution. He further advised the project team to actively disseminate results to stakeholders and relevant actors and recommended to submit an ArcSolution-related action to the Mission Ocean and Waters Charter to enhance its reach and policy impact.

The presentation by ArcSolution's Project Officer, Izabela Freytag, followed John Hanus's talk. She guided participants through key aspects of the Grant Agreement, outlining project requirements and expectations set by the European Commission. Izabela Freytag emphasized the importance of maintaining clear communication channels, both for fostering an open dialogue between the project team and the Project Officer and for disseminating project results and publications. She highlighted the official communication channels provided by the European Commission, which are essential for ensuring that outcomes are effectively shared with relevant stakeholders and the broader community.

The ArcSolution Objectives

During a session dedicated to the project's overall objectives, the Work Package (WP) leaders shared insights from their respective areas and presented the conceptual basis for each WP. They discussed the One Health approach and addressed the presence and transport of contaminants such as PFAS, plastics, and mercury in the Arctic environment. The project's relevance to the quadruple planetary crisis—encompassing climate change, pollution, biodiversity loss, and zoonoses—was emphasized.

The WP leaders outlined how ArcSolution can contribute to potential solutions and mitigation strategies through circular processes. They posed research questions focusing on reducing

contamination from local sources, including hospitals, industrial plants, sewage systems, and solid waste management. Additionally, they highlighted the critical role of effective communication and dissemination efforts to maximize the project's impact across relevant channels and stakeholders.

International collaboration

The ArcSolution project is closely aligned with key policies and international governing structures, including the Arctic Council, and the Stockholm and Minamata Conventions of the United Nations Environment Program (UNEP). Representatives of these organizations had been invited to provide their take on important issues in their domains and potential contributions from ArcSolution. The session began with Mario Acquarone, Deputy Manager of the Arctic Monitoring and Assessment Program (AMAP) secretariat, who provided participants with a historical overview of AMAP and explained its connections to policymakers. He outlined how ArcSolution relates to the Arctic Council through the working groups of the Arctic Council, including AMAP, Emergency, Prevention, Preparedness and Response (EPPR), and Protection of the Marine Environment (PAME).

Next, Timo Seppälä, a Senior Officer at the Finnish Environment Institute, and an expert on international chemicals conventions, discussed the ongoing efforts of the Stockholm Convention and how ArcSolution can contribute to identifying hazardous chemicals and collecting data for risk assessment purposes. He underscored the importance of distinguishing between local sources of pollution and long-range environmental transport, and he encouraged researchers to provide insights on this matter when disseminating new knowledge about Arctic contaminants.

Photo 2: Timo Seppälä discussed how ArcSolution can influence and contribute to policy development on chemical management.

The session concluded with Katrin Vorkamp (Aarhus University, Denmark) presenting the Horizon Europe Partnership for the Assessment of Risks from Chemicals (PARC), co-funded by the EU Commission. The partnership aims to develop next-generation chemical risk assessments to protect human health and the environment, involving over 200 institutions across 28 countries and three EU agencies. Katrin Vorkamp co-leads the task on Environmental and Multisource Monitoring in PARC and pointed at areas of common interest in PARC and ArcSolution, such as

PFAS and plastic additives, and approaches that involve human biomonitoring and environmental monitoring. She emphasized how ArcSolution can enhance understanding of chemical risks through the One Health approach.

Sister projects

Representatives from ArcSolution's sister projects, ILLUQ (Leena-Kaisa Viitanen, Alfred-Wegener-Institute, Germany and Alexandra Meyer, University of Vienna, Austria) and ICEBERG (Adam Stepien, University of Lapland, Finland), presented their respective initiatives and fostered a dialogue on potential synergies among the three projects. Approximately one hour of the programme was dedicated to open discussions of collaboration possibilities. The participants explored collaborative measures and activities throughout the project duration, focusing on several key areas.

Data sharing emerged as a critical topic, along with collaboration on community meetings and coordination of outreach efforts. The representatives emphasized the importance of involving local institutions at joint study sites, such as Longyearbyen and the Mackenzie Delta region. They also discussed the development of joint policy briefs and thematic online workshops, as well as citizen science initiatives. Additionally, the possibility of organizing joint sessions at major Arctic conferences was highlighted, underscoring the potential for greater impact through collaboration.

Photo 3: Representatives from the three projects. From the left: Irene Andreassen, Alexandra Meyer, Leena-Kaisa Viitanen, Arja Rautio, Jon Øyvind Odland and Adam Stepien.

ArcSolution educational profile and UArctic connections

Roland Kallenborn (Norwegian University of Life Science) presented ArcSolution's educational profile and initiated a discussion on how to take this further. Discussions highlighted the need to prepare the next generation of Arctic health and environment researchers. Practical planning for the number of PhD and postdoctoral positions is essential, with plans for ArcSolutions will involve

several postdocs and PhDs over different Work Packages. Senior researchers expressed their willingness to mentor and support of a Young Researcher Network., while. Roland Kallenborn noted UArctic's funding for an educational programme with links to ArcSolution, including a summer school program. Practical planning for the number of PhD and postdoctoral positions is essential, with plans for several postdocs and PhDs over different Work Packages.

Re-establishing a research school for Arctic health Health was proposed, with potential cooperation through UArctic's existing study programs. Upcoming events, like the planned One Health PhD course before back-to-back with the Nunamed NUNAMED conference in Nuuk in October 2025, offer further educational collaboration opportunities.

Participants discussed exchange projects, with Roland Kallenborn mentioning available funding, including Erasmus opportunities. The ILLUQ project noted young researchers' ability to self-organize, while the need for an online platform for researcher recruitment was also suggested.

These discussions reflect an commitment to interest in strengthening educational ties within ArcSolution and UArctic, aiming to support future Arctic researchers.

View of the external advisors

The two External advisors Advisors for ArcSolution, Derek Muir from Environment and Climate Change Canada and Elisabete Weiderpass from the International Agency for Research on Cancer (IARC) highlighted the significance of the ArcSolution project, praising in particular its holistic approach that integrates local and indigenous knowledge. They mentioned technical and scientific developments in the field that ArcSolution might want to consider and They emphasized the delicate balance that indigenous peoples maintain between environmental preservation and human activities. This project represents a groundbreaking model for addressing global health issues by linking diverse knowledge systems and fostering collaboration across various fields of expertise.

Joint social event in the evening

Nord University hosted a joint dinner for all participants from Day 1 of the ArcSolution kick-off meeting at a local restaurant (LystPå, Bodø), fostering continued conversation and networking among the projects and external guests.

Photo 4: The evening social and networking dinner at “LystPå” provided a relaxed and inviting atmosphere for participants to connect and engage with one another.

4 Day 2 – internal housekeeping, activities, milestones and deliverables

Day 2 began with a warm welcome to Noatun, the newly opened building of the Faculty of Biosciences and Aquaculture at Nord University, delivered by Faculty Director Jarle Jørgensen.

Finances, reporting and data management

This section was presented by Irene Andreassen (Nord University, Norway), the administrative project manager for ArcSolution. She outlined the main reporting requirements and book-keeping rules from the Grant Agreement concerning personnel and travel costs. Irene Andreassen emphasized the importance of the project handbook, stating that it is mandatory reading for all partners. The handbook includes essential information, such as the Quality Assurance Protocol, and it is crucial for all partners to understand the management's expectations. The handbook is enclosed at the end of this document. Additionally, the session covered internal communication and data management practices within the project.

First year of ArcSolution, activities, milestones and deliverables

The next session featured the work package leaders, who each presented their planned activities according to the project plan. They emphasized key milestones for the first year and highlighted upcoming deadlines, as well as showcasing some work that had already commenced and the progress made in these activities, such as community meetings in WP2 and the start of discussions and preparations in WP3 on priority pollutants and non-target screening. Additionally, the session focused on cross-cutting activities and the interdependencies among the various work packages and tasks, stressing the importance of maintaining effective communication and information flow throughout the project.

Study areas and citizen science

Julia Olsen (Nord University, Norway) provided updates from the location-specific consultation meetings within ArcSolution, emphasizing how these activities integrate with other tasks and work packages across the project. Meetings have already taken place in Svalbard (Longyearbyen) and Greenland (Nuuk and Tasiilaq), and Julia Olsen outlined plans for upcoming meetings in Northern Norway (Tromsø and Skjervøy) and Northern Finland (Inari).

Photo 5: Julia Olsen presents the work on the study areas.

Riita-Marja Leinonen and Anna Rönkä (University of Oulu, Finland) then presented on the ArcSolution project’s approach to Citizen Science (CS), covering our interpretation of the term, examples of other CS projects in Arctic regions, and how CS is being implemented within ArcSolution. They showed which CS projects are pre-defined in the ArcSolution work plan and discussed the role of schools at the four study locations, which could also be involved in CS activities.

Following this, Katrin Vorkamp led a discussion on our approach to the various study areas. She summarized location-specific activities that are proposed in the project description and potential activities that were discussed in the consultation meetings. Upcoming meetings with the municipality in Tromsø and schools in Northern Norway in November 2024 will further add to the material collected at the consultation meetings. Activities in Longyearbyen might include studies on wastewater and indoor air quality, but need further discussion and planning, also involving the local population. The discussion also revealed a need for systematic overviews of existing human samples and data, as a basis for decisions on new measurements of the priority pollutants in ArcSolution. Furthermore, the role of associated partners was discussed with a view to harmonised approaches to different study locations as well as support of theoretical work on e.g. reviews and inventories.

Photo 6: Discussion on the approach to the study areas, led by Katrin Vorkamp.

Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication

Lars-Otto Reiersen (Arctic Knowledge, Norway) provided an update on the ongoing work with the Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication plan, focusing on identifying key stakeholders and target groups. He emphasized the importance of engaging schools and students not as passive listeners, but as active participants through co-creation methods, where students will also play an active role in communicating the project results.

Marta Anna Løvberg (Nordland Research Institute, Norway) contributed technical insights, highlighting the need for a streamlined approach to communication efforts. She outlined plans for establishing social media channels and a project website, and shared general guidelines on communicating project results.

Conclusions and next steps

The kick-off meeting concluded with a panel discussion with the WP leaders, who shared their impressions of the meeting and their perspectives on the path ahead. They unanimously agreed that the project has had a strong start and emphasized the importance of continued collaboration across work packages and disciplines to achieve the best possible outcomes.

Photo 7: WP-leaders in the concluding panel – reflecting on the way forward

5 Agenda for the kick-off meeting

Wednesday 23rd October (Scandic Bodø)

Time	What	Who
08:30 – 09:00	Registration - coffee	
09:00 – 09:30	Welcome to Bodø	Jon Øyvind Odland (NORD) Odd Emil Ingebrigtsen (Mayor of Bodø municipality) Mette Sørensen (Dean of Faculty for Bioscience and Aquaculture, Nord University)
09:30 – 09:45	The ArcSolution vision	Jon Øyvind Odland (NORD)
09:45 – 10:15	Presentation of the participants	All
10:15 – 10:45	Information by ArcSolution project officers	Izabela Freytag (EU Commission) John Hanus (EU Commission)
10:45 – 11:00	Coffee break	
11:00 – 12:00	The ArcSolution objectives	WP-leaders
12:00 – 13:00	Lunch	
13:00 – 13:30	International collaboration AMAP/Arctic Council UNEP Stockholm and Minamata Convention PARC	Mario Acquarone (AMAP) Timo Seppälä (Finnish Environment Institute) Katrin Vorkamp (AU)
13:30 – 14:45	Presentations of ICEBERG and ILLUQ incl. suggestions for collaboration Followed by a joint discussion on collaboration possibilities	Alexandra Meyer (ILLUQ) Leena-Kaisa Viitanen (ILLUQ) Adam Stepien (ICEBERG) Moderated by Arja Rautio and Jon Øyvind Odland (UOULU + NORD)
14:45 – 15:15	Coffee break	
15:15 – 16:15	ArcSolution – Education profile incl. UArctic connection Open discussion	Roland Kallenborn (NMBU)
16:15 – 16:45	View of the external advisors	Elisabete Weiderpass (IARC Director) Derek Muir (Environment and Climate Change Canada)
16:45 - 17:00	Wrap up of the day + group photo	Jon Øyvind and Irene (NORD)
19:00	Dinner at “LystPå” (https://www.lystpa.no/) Storgata 7A Bodø City centre	

Thursday 24th October – Noatun, Nord University Campus

Time	What	Who
09:00	Bus transport from Scandic Bodø to Nord University campus	
09:20 – 09:30	Welcome to Noatun	Jarle Jørgensen (Faculty Director, Nord University)
09:30 – 10:00	Finances and reporting Project handbook Data management plan	Irene Andreassen (NORD)
10:00 – 10:45	The first year – activities, milestones and deliverables WP1, 2, 3	WP leaders
10:45 – 11:15	Coffee break	
11:15 – 12:00	The first year – activities, milestones and deliverables WP4, 5, 6	WP leaders
12:00 – 13:00	Lunch	
13:00 – 13:30	Citizen science projects in ArcSolution	Anna Rönkä (UOULU) Riitta-Marja Leinonen (UOULU)
13:30 – 13:45	Updates from location-specific consultation meetings	Julia Olsen (NORD) Jon Øyvind Odland (NORD)
13:45 – 15:00	Study areas – joint activities	Katrin Vorkamp (AU)
15:00 – 15:30	Coffee break	
15:30 – 16:00	Study areas – joint activities/summarize	Katrin Vorkamp (AU)
16:00 – 16:30	Communication plan - stakeholders and target groups	Lars-Otto Reiersen (AKn)
16:30 – 17:00	Conclusions and next steps Panel with WP-leads	Jon Øyvind Odland (NORD)
17:15 – 17:45	Bus transport from University Campus to Saltstraumen	
18:00	Dinner at Tuvsjyen (https://tuvsjyen.com)	
21:00	Return to Bodø/Scandic by bus	

Project Handbook

Abstract:

The Project Handbook provides guidelines for members of the ArcSolution project, covering key aspects such as management structures, project reporting and working practices. While some of these topics are only briefly addressed here, they are or will be detailed more formally in the Grant Agreement, Consortium Agreement, Communication and Dissemination plan and the Data Management Plan. This handbook is prepared for reference and will be revised as needed as procedures evolve throughout the project.

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1 Project Management Structures

1.1 Principles

The management structures of ArcSolution are designed to efficiently coordinate the organization of the project on three different levels:

- (i) Interaction between the European Commission and the project,
- (ii) Collaboration between project partners
- (iii) Coordination and monitoring of daily work through mechanisms for financial, quality, risk, communication and progress management.

These management structures are described in the Grant Agreement (WP1) and formalized in the Consortium Agreement. The summary below outlines some of the main features. Detailed procedures for meetings, agendas, and voting are included in the Consortium Agreement and are not reproduced in this handbook.

While the formal collaboration guidelines are outlined in the consortium agreement, it's equally important to create a positive and supportive working environment.

We're committed to making this project a success—and having fun along the way!

1.2 Governance structure

The governance structure of ArcSolution includes three primary bodies, each supported by a Quality and Ethical Board (QEB) and an External Advisory Board (EAB) for scientific input. The QEB and EAB do not manage ArcSolution directly but contribute to ethical requirements, strategy, and overall project progress and impact assessment. The bodies are as follows:

- General Assembly (GEA): Highest decision-making body.
- Executive Board (EXB): Responsible for day-to-day management and implementation of decisions by the General Assembly.
- Project Coordination Office (PCO): Administration, management and support body.

- Quality and Ethics Board (QEB): Oversees ethical compliance and Quality Assurance of projects deliverables
- External Advisory Board (EAB): Provides scientific advice.

1.2.1 General Assembly (GEA)

All partners have one seat in the GEA, which will meet once a year to oversee the progress in the project according to the Grant Agreement and Consortium Agreement and to agree on strategic actions needed to reach milestones and deliverables. The meetings of the General Assembly will be prepared by the Project Coordination Office, on behalf of the Executive Committee. The Chair of the Executive Committee is also the Chair of the General Assembly.

1.2.2 Executive Board (EXB)

The Executive Board (EXB), consisting of the work package leaders, is responsible for implementation of the project according to the description of the action. It guides the Project Coordination Office in preparing meetings with the General Assembly and advisory bodies. The EXB holds frequent online meetings and face-to-face meetings.

The EXB, acting as the supervisory body for the execution of the project, reports to and is accountable to the General Assembly. Additionally, the EXB serves as the unit for resolving potential conflicts.

Local representatives (one per site from each of the four study locations) will be formally invited to join the EXB meetings twice a year. Before participating, they will sign a Non-Disclosure Agreement (NDA) with terms similar to those in the Consortium Agreement, which will be signed by all parties. The local representatives will have the right to speak at the meetings but will not have voting rights.

1.2.3 Project Coordination Office (PCO)

The Project Coordination Office (PCO) is responsible for daily internal coordination among the project's bodies, communication with the European Commission on reports and financial matters, and meeting preparation in consultation with the Executive Committee (EXC). The PCO consists of the Project Coordinator, the Project Manager, and other supporting staff at the coordination entity, including financial controllers, legal advisors, and additional support services as needed. The Project Officer at the European Commission will communicate exclusively with the Project Coordinator as the single point of contact to ArcSolution. Therefore, any questions or concerns for the European Commission must be directed to the PCO first. The only exception is if the General

Assembly raises concerns about the coordination of the project. This case is further described in the Consortium Agreement.

1.2.4 Quality and Ethics Board (QEB)

The Quality and Ethics Board (QEB) consists of 4 consortium partners and is responsible for reviewing, approving, and applying legal and ethical requirements. They ensure adherence to relevant legislation, and general research ethics procedures as well as to the guidelines outlined in the Data Management Plan. Led by the Ethics Board Manager, the QEB oversees project activities to ensure compliance with ethical standards and addresses any ethical issues that arise during implementation. Additionally, the QEB is responsible for the quality assurance of the project's deliverables.

1.2.5 External Advisory Board (EAB)

The Executive Committee (EXC) will appoint the External Advisory Board (EAB), which will consist of two international experts. The EAB members will provide scientific and organizational advice on the project and might also be consulted on strategic matters, offering independent opinions. Their engagement will involve online meetings as needed and invitations to the annual in-person consortium meetings. The EAB members do not receive remuneration of their time, while travel expenses are covered by the project.

1.2.6 Work Package Management

Each Work Package (WPs) will be led by a designated Work Package Leaders from one of partner organizations. These leaders coordinate, supervise, and actively contribute to the activities within their WPs, reporting back to the Executive Board (EXB) and Project Coordination Office (PCO).

WP Leaders are tasked with monitoring progress against planned deliverables and milestones, assessing risks, and proposing contingency plans as needed. They regularly update the EXB on the status of their WPs.

As members of the EXB, WP Leaders also provide task leaders and other team members within the WP with relevant information from the EXB, hosting regular online meetings to keep all participants informed about progress and developments.

2 Project reporting and financial management

2.1 Project reporting

There are three main types of reporting in ArcSolution:

1. Formal reports to the European Commission (EC)
2. Internal report to the Project Coordinator for the pre-financing (M12)
3. 6-monthly reports to the Project Officer

Formal reporting to the EC:

- 1st Reporting: 18 months after project start
- 2nd Reporting: 36 months after project start
- 3rd (final) Reporting: 48 months after project start

Reporting is conducted through the EC's funding and tender platform, which outlines the necessary contents: primarily, a **periodic technical report** and a **financial report**. These reports must be submitted within 60 days after the end of each reporting period.

The PCO is responsible for preparing the technical report, report with contributions from the WP leaders. Additionally, all funded partners must submit individual financial statements to the coordinator (through the EC portal) detailing their eligible costs for the period, adhering to the regulations specified in the Grant Agreement.

Internal reports to the coordinator:

For the payment of the remaining pre-financing after the first 12 months, each partner will also need to provide the following information to the coordinator (not through the EC portal):

- Staff effort expended in person-months over the preceding 12 months
- Summary of all personal costs
- Summary of non-staff costs such as travel, equipment, fieldwork/workshop costs etc.

6-monthly reports to the Project Officer

Short progress reports are required by the project officer (PO) every 6 months, including:

- Brief written reports on activities, for dissemination purposes

- Updates on progress toward deliverables, identification of risks and issues, and planned activities
- A short summary of attended meetings

2.2 Financial Management

Each partner is accountable for managing their expenses in accordance with the budget and regulations outlined in the Grant Agreement (GA).

The PCO can provide general support and advice in cases involving concerns about eligible costs, reporting requirements, and similar matters.

Eligible costs are described in Article 6 of the GA.

The costs can be one of the following categories:

- personnel cost
- travel cost
- equipment cost
- other goods and services
- subcontracting costs (only if planned beforehand in the proposal)

To be eligible, actual costs must meet the following criteria:

- They must be actually incurred by the beneficiary.
- They should be incurred within the project period, except for costs related to the submission of the final periodic report, which may be incurred afterward.
- They must fall under one of the budget categories.
- They must be incurred in connection with the action as described in Annex 1 of the Grant Agreement and be necessary for its implementation (linked to the action).
- They should be identifiable and verifiable, specifically recorded in the beneficiary's accounts in accordance with the applicable accounting standards in their country and their usual cost accounting practices.
- They must comply with applicable national laws on taxes, labor, and social security.
- They should be reasonable, justified, and adhere to the principles of sound financial management, particularly regarding economy and efficiency.

2.2.1 Record keeping for personnel costs

There are two options for keeping records on personnel costs.

All partners may either:

- By default, sign a monthly declaration on day-equivalents (normally 8 hours per day) worked for the action

OR

- Use another paper- or computer-based reliable time recording system, to record all the time (days/hours) worked for the action. The system must include two approvals: one from the individual and one from a supervisor or equivalent authority who can verify the timesheet.

A template for the monthly declaration is enclosed in annex 1.

2.2.2 Travel cost

General principles for travel cost:

1. Report all actual travel costs in accordance with your organization's accounting principles and travel policy. Ensure that all costs are properly documented and consistent with your organization's established procedures.
2. Travel must be directly linked to the project action and should be reported in the periodic financial report. It is recommended to complete a mission report form, which includes a brief abstract detailing who traveled, to where, and for what purpose.
3. Travel costs are primarily eligible for personnel who are working directly on the project. Ensure that only relevant personnel costs are included in the financial report in the same period as the travel.
4. For travels with multiple purposes (e.g., combining trips for different projects or both professional and private reasons), ensure that travel costs are proportionately allocated and reported only for the project-related portion.
5. Ensure that travel aligns with your timesheets to accurately reflect the time spent on the project. This ensures consistency between travel costs and recorded work time on the project.

2.2.3 Indirect cost / overhead cost

Overhead is applied at a flat rate of 25% to all personnel costs, travel expenses, equipment costs, and other goods and services. However, it is not applied to subcontracting costs.

No documentation is required for the 25% overhead, as it is automatically added to the reported costs in the portal.

3 Deliverables, Milestones and Quality Assurance

3.1 Deliverables process

Our project's success depends on the timely and high-quality delivery of outputs, known as deliverables, which include reports, datasets, publications, and other tangible outcomes. This section outlines the process for defining, producing, and ensuring the quality of deliverables throughout the project lifecycle.

In Section 3.3, you will find a table listing all deliverables along with their respective deadlines, while Section 3.4 provides a similar table for milestones. A full description and detailed information for each deliverable and milestone are available in the Description of Action (part A), beginning on page 19. This document is available in Teams in the following folder: “WP1” – “Grant agreement and consortium agreement”.

Timelines of the ArcSolution project, with deliverables and milestones per year are given in appendix 2 (also available in Teams as ppt documents).

Figure 1: Q/E assurance procedure timeline

3.2 Quality Assurance Procedures for Deliverables

1. Ten weeks prior to the due date, the respective deliverable will be on the agenda of an EXB meeting, to ensure agreement on its content and the further process. Subsequently, the EXB will find a suitable peer-reviewer in the consortium who is not directly involved with the production of the deliverable.
2. The partner responsible for the deliverable submits a complete draft to the Work Package (WP) leader at least 8 weeks before the deadline. The WP leader reviews the draft within two weeks, and the responsible partner revises it within two weeks.
3. The WP-leader forwards the revised draft for to the Quality and Ethics Board (QEB) and the selected peer-reviewer at least four (4) weeks before the due date.
4. The peer-reviewer conducts a scientific review, while the QEB checks that ethical standards are met.
 - a. Feedback from the QEB and internal peer-reviewers must be submitted to the responsible partner no later than two weeks before the deliverable's due date, copied to the WP-leader
5. The partner responsible for the deliverable revises it based on the feedback provided and returns it to the PCO, copied to the WP-leader
6. The revised deliverable undergoes a final check for control, format, and compliance by the Project Coordination Office (PCO), at least five working days before the due date.
7. The PCO uploads the final version to the portal and submits the deliverable.

3.3 Overview of all Deliverables

In the tables below all the project deliverables are listed, with responsible partner and due date.

WP1 Management and administration

Number	Title	Lead partner	Due date
D1.1	Kick-off meeting	NORD	30 th Nov. 24
D1.2	Data Management Plan	NORD	31 st Jan. 25
D1.3	International cooperation	NORD	30 th Nov. 27
D1.4	Data Management Plan - midterm	NORD	31 st Jul. 26
D1.5	Data Management Plan - conclusions	NORD	31 st Jul. 28

WP2 The ArcSolution One Health framework

Number	Title	Lead partner	Due date
D2.1	1st One Health Model	UOULU	30 th Apr. 25
D2.2	Description of citizen science projects	UOULU	31 st May 25
D2.3	Data gaps	UOULU	31 st Jul. 25
D2.4	2nd One Health Model	UOULU	30 th Apr. 26
D2.5	3rd One Health Model	UOULU	30 Apr. 27
D2.6	4th One Health Model	UOULU	30 th Apr. 28
D2.7	Policy brief 1	UOULU	31 st Oct. 25

WP3 Arctic Pollution in a climate change context

Number	Title	Lead partner	Due date
D3.1	Priority pollutants	AU	31 st May 25
D3.2	Non-target screening pollutants	AU	31 st Jan. 27
D3.3	Litter source identification	NMBU	31 st Jul. 27
D3.4	Exposure of local communities	UOULU	31 st Dec. 27
D3.5	Long-range transport of (micro-)plastics	AU	31 st Oct. 27
D3.6	Results for the local model	NMBU	30 th Nov. 27
D3.7	Modelling and measurement results for an Arctic foodweb	AU	30 th Nov. 27

WP4 Impacts under different scenarios

Number	Title	Lead partner	Due date
D4.1	Effect-directed analyses	AU	31 st Mar. 26
D4.2	Effects of plastics	AU	31 st May 27
D4.3	Impact report	UOULU	29 th Feb. 28

D4.4	Zoonosis and transfer of antimicrobial resistant bacteria between Arctic wildlife and humans	NMBU	30 th Nov. 27
D4.5	Physiological changes in Arctic animals	NMBU	30 th Sep. 27

WP5 Solutions - Resilience, adaptation, mitigation

Number	Title	Lead partner	Due date
D5.1	Locally prioritized solutions	NMBU	31 st Jan. 27
D5.2	Indicator compounds and matrices	NMBU	30 th Nov. 27
D5.3	Mitigation methods	NMBU	31 st Mar. 28
D5.4	Circular remediation of Arctic pollutions	NMBU	31 st Mar. 28
D5.5	Meta-database	NMBU	30 th Jun. 27
D5.6	Solutions for remediation and reduction of emissions	NMBU	31 st Mar. 28

WP6 Exploitation, Dissemination and Communication

Number	Title	Lead partner	Due date
D6.1	Webpage and social media accounts	AKn	30 th Nov. 24
D6.2	Exploitation, communication and dissemination plan	AKn	31 st Jan. 25
D6.3	Citizen science projects	UOULU	31 st Mar. 28
D6.4	Teaching material	AKn	30 th Apr. 28
D6.5	Conference report	NORD	31 st Jul. 28
D6.6	Concluding exploitation, communication and dissemination report.	AKn	30 th Jun. 28
D6.7	Policy brief 2	AKn	31 st May 28

3.4 Milestones

ArcSolution milestones are specific points in the project timeline that allow us to track key moments and completed activities. These milestones help us monitor the project's progress and ensure deadlines are met on schedule.

Reporting milestones is straightforward, involving only a checkbox, and is managed by the PCO. Partners responsible for one or more milestones must ensure that the planned activities are completed on time. They should promptly report to the PCO any delays in reaching a milestone.

In the tables below all the project Milestones are listed, with responsible partner and due date.

WP1 Management and administration

Number	Title	Lead partner	Due date
M1.1	Kick-off meeting	NORD	31 st Oct. 24
M1.2	1 st Consortium meeting	NORD	31 st Oct. 25
M1.3	Cooperation with relevant projects	NORD	31 st Mar. 26
M1.4	2 nd Consortium meeting	NORD	31 st Oct. 26
M1.5	3 rd Consortium meeting	NORD	31 st Oct. 27
M1.6	Establishment of the Ethical Board	NORD	30 th Sep. 24

WP2 The ArcSolution One Health framework

Number	Title	Lead partner	Due date
M2.1	Introductory workshop (WS) at each location	UOULU	31 st Jan. 25
M2.2	1st follow up of WS at each location	UOULU	31 st Jan 26
M2.3	2nd follow up of WS at each location	UOULU	31 st Jan 27
M2.4	3rd follow up of WS at each location	UOULU	31 st Jan 28

WP3 Arctic Pollution in a climate change context

Number	Title	Lead partner	Due date
M3.1	Emission inventories	AU	31 st Jan 26
M3.2	Microplastics in snow	AU	31 st Mar. 26
M3.3	Non-target screening	AU	31 st Jul. 26
M3.4	Indoor environment	UOULU	31 st Mar. 27
M3.5	Wastewater treatment effects	NMBU	31 st Jul. 27

WP4 Impacts under different scenarios

Number	Title	Lead partner	Due date
M4.1	Gut microbiome	NMBU	31 st Jan. 27

M4.2	Effect-directed analyses	AU	31 st Jan. 27
M4.3	Histopathological and immunohistochemical studies	NMBU	31 st Jul. 27

WP5 Solutions - Resilience, adaptation, mitigation

Number	Title	Lead partner	Due date
M5.1	Indicator compounds and matrices	NMBU	31 st Mar 26
M5.2	Monitoring of local pollutant mitigation	NMBU	31 st May 26
M5.3	Technological solutions	NMBU	31 st Jul. 27
M5.4	Guidelines for decision-makers	NMBU	30 th Nov. 27

WP6 Exploitation, Dissemination and Communication

Number	Title	Lead partner	Due date
M6.1	School cooperation	Akn	30 th Nov. 27
M6.2	Dissemination of citizen science projects	Akn	30 th Nov. 27
M6.3	Final conference	NORD	30 th Apr. 28
M6.4	Webpage	Akn	30 th Sep. 24

4 Collaboration and internal Communications

4.1 Internal communication channels

ArcSolution employs several internal communication tools to ensure effective collaboration among partners.

Collaboration on external communication and dissemination is detailed in the Communication, dissemination and exploitation plan (will come in Annex 3). Preparations of scientific publications will follow separate guidelines.

The following are the key channels for internal communication:

4.1.1 Microsoft Teams

Microsoft Teams serves as the primary platform for document storage and collaborative work. It is also the preferred tool for online meetings, though Zoom or other platforms can be used when necessary.

If you do not have access to the ArcSolution Teams workspace, please contact the project manager for assistance. The Teams workspace is registered under Nord University, so if you are affiliated with another institution, ensure you switch to the correct affiliation when logging in.

The file directory in Teams is organized by work packages (WPs), with a dedicated folder for each WP. You may create new folders or channels if your documents involve multiple WPs.

For WP-related meetings, it is essential to upload meeting minutes to the appropriate folder for easy reference and future audits.

Documents on the project Teams site are internal documents, including drafts, which are only intended for the project participants. None of these unpublished documents should be shared with individuals or organizations outside the ArcSolution consortium, without prior consultation of the Executive Board.

4.1.2 E-mailing lists

To facilitate group communication, use the contact list available in the WP1 folder on Teams to copy and paste email addresses for different institutions. Managing email lists can be challenging, with risks of outdated contacts, so it's recommended to always check for updates.

As a courtesy to your colleagues, ensure that relevant individuals are included in the email recipients. Additionally, upload any shared documents to Teams to maintain transparency and a single source of information.

Some communication might be sent only to the primary contact person for each partner (see list on p. 2). It is the responsibility of the primary contact person to forward relevant information to the right person in the partner organization.

4.1.3 Online meetings

In addition to the meetings described in section 1, online meetings are organized as needed, for example at the project, WP, or task level. If you need to record a meeting, always obtain consent from participants.

It is advisable to avoid using third-party services for recording or transcription outside of Microsoft Teams, as these may not meet required data security standards, especially regarding personal data sharing.

4.1.4 Face-to-face meetings

Throughout the project, there will be four in-person meetings, plus a final conference. All ArcSolution partners are expected to attend these events. The planned meetings are as follows:

- 2024: Bodø – Kick-off meeting (23rd – 24th October)
- 2025: [Location TBD]
- 2026: [Location TBD]
- 2027: [Location TBD]
- 2028: Final Conference

Additional face-to-face meetings may be organized at the WP or task level or in connection with other activities. Partners are encouraged to make the most of travel opportunities by scheduling meetings during scientific conferences or other relevant events to maximize efficiency.

4.1.5 Minutes of the meetings

Meeting minutes for all ArcSolution meetings should be documented using the provided templates, available in the WP6 folder under 'Templates'. Once completed, upload the minutes to the appropriate WP folder in Teams to ensure transparency and maintain a clear record of discussions and decisions.

4.1.6 Internal newsletter

The Project Manager will prepare and circulate internal newsletters approximately every 1-2 months. Contributions from all partners are essential, as the Project Coordination Office (PCO) cannot track all ongoing activities. Whenever possible, please include photos and a brief written summary of relevant events or updates.

5 Roles and Responsibilities

5.1 Consortium partners and roles

Each consortium partner plays a key role in the project. Some lead work packages or tasks, while others handle deliverables or milestones. Regardless of the role, everyone contributes to our shared goals, which are essential for achieving the desired impact.

If any challenges, delays, or concerns arise, it is important to bring them up as soon as possible to prevent issues like delays or low-quality outcomes. The PCO of ArcSolution will always be open for input, ensuring we stay on track and address any concerns early.

While the formal collaboration guidelines are outlined in the consortium agreement, it is equally important to create a positive and supportive working environment. We're committed to making this project a success—and having fun along the way! 😊

5.2 Responsibilities of each partner

Each partner is responsible for:

- Monitoring their budget and expenses, ensuring financial bookkeeping is in line with the Grant Agreement and national legislations, and making sure the allocated resources are sufficient for the entire project duration.
- Contributing to the technical implementation of the project, in accordance with the timeline and quality standards
- Maintaining open and transparent communication, involving fellow partners whenever necessary
- Contributing to both internal and external reports through deliverables, milestones, communication efforts, or similar, as outlined in the project plan
- Informing the WP-leader and the PCO as soon as possible if any deviations from the project plan or budget arises
- Actively engaging in cross-partner collaboration and knowledge sharing, especially in areas where synergy between partners can enhance project outcomes.

Annex 1: Monthly declaration of hours worked on the project

EU GRANTS DECLARATION OF DAYS WORKED ON A PROJECT			YEAR:	
<i>To be kept on file in case of audits.</i>				
Project acronym:	ArcSolution	Project number:	101135051	
Participant name:				
Name of the person:		Type of personnel: (employee/ natural person under direct contract/ seconded/ other)		
Month	Days worked in the action ¹ (e.g. 15; 7,5; 0,5; 0,25)	Work Packages worked on (e.g. WP2; WP5)	Date and signature of the person	Name, date and signature of the supervisor
January			Signature: Date:	Name: Signature: Date:
February			Signature: Date:	Name: Signature: Date:
March			Signature: Date:	Name: Signature: Date:
April			Signature: Date:	Name: Signature: Date:
May			Signature: Date:	Name: Signature: Date:
June			Signature: Date:	Name: Signature: Date:
July			Signature: Date:	Name: Signature: Date:
August			Signature: Date:	Name: Signature: Date:
September			Signature: Date:	Name: Signature: Date:
October			Signature: Date:	Name: Signature: Date:
November			Signature: Date:	Name: Signature: Date:
December			Signature: Date:	Name: Signature: Date:
TOTAL				

¹ 1 day = number of hours that a full-time employee of the participant has to work in a standard day (e.g. 8 hours).

Annex 2: Timelines of the project with Deliverables and Milestones

Year 2

🚩 = official deliverable ✓ = official milestone

Year 3

🚩 = official deliverable ✓ = official milestone

Year 4

Other Appendices (will come)

1. Consortium agreement
 2. Communication and dissemination plan
 3. Data Management Plan
 4. Contact information for project partners and stakeholders
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